

Correct original spelling of *Probosciphaedusa gongjin* Chen *et al.*, 2026

ZHE-YU CHEN¹ & ZHONG-GUANG CHEN²

¹ Faculty of Science, The University of Melbourne, Parkville VIC 3010, Australia

² Shanghai Natural History Museum, Branch of Shanghai Science and Technology Museum, Jingan, Shanghai 200000, China

Corresponding author: Z.-Y. Chen (chenzheyu1998@163.com)

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Chen *et al.* (2026) introduced the clausiliid species *Probosciphaedusa gongjin* Z.-G. Chen, Z.-Y. Chen, Z.-J. Xu, F. Li & S. Li, 2026 from Hubei Province, China. It has come to our attention that this species name is spelled in more than one way in the original publication, namely *P. gongjin* and *P. gongjini*. We hereby select *P. gongjin* as the correct original spelling of the species name in accordance with Article 32.2.1 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 1999). Although the form *P. gongjin* appears only in the description section, this is where the name is formally introduced. Moreover, the etymological statement indicates that the name is used as a noun in apposition, confirming that *P. gongjin* corresponds to the authors' intended

original spelling. Although the alternative spelling *P. gongjini* appears five times elsewhere in the text, this does not affect the determination above.

REFERENCES

- ICZN (INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON ZOOLOGICAL NOMENCLATURE). 1999. *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. Fourth Edition*. The International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature, London, xxix + 306 pp.
- CHEN Z.-G., CHEN Z.-Y., XU Z.-J., LI F., LI S. 2026. Four new species of door snail from China (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora: Clausiliidae: Phaedusinae). *Journal of Conchology* **45** (5): 814–821. doi: 10.61733/jconch/4569